

The Effectiveness of Using Technology in Learning English

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ABSTRACT

This study found out about the effectiveness of using technology in learning English. However, few studies have been shown the effectiveness of technology in all English skills: Speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. Third-year students of the Foreign Language Department at Van Lang University participated in this study for two weeks. The questions revolved around learning English and using technology in learning English. The researchers collected all the responses. The goal of using technology in learning English brings a strong potential to enhance learners' language skills and promote the process of learning English quickly. After using technology in learning English, we examined the impacts of the teaching on the four skills, and this effect is expressed as a percentage (30%, 50%, 80%) based on the results obtained from the questionnaires.

Keywords: *Technology, learning English, the effectiveness of using technology, English skills.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the study

There has been a lot of research on using technology in learning English. Himmelsbach (2019) stated that when the Internet is connected, we can access and collect information 24 hours a day. Moreover, we can find almost everything on the Internet, and it has regularly updated versions. For students, this access helps them find study materials and learning software to interact and open resources from famous universities in the world. Using technology in learning is an online world where learners use their image as their profile picture to immerse themselves in one place with various contexts. Second Life offers students chances to connect and to cooperate with other learners while away from classes. Moreover, the learners can discover and communicate with the other and immerse themselves in the language they are learning (Zazulak, 2016). One of the benefits of using technology in learning English is engaging students in new ways. According to Arifah (2014), accessing

the Internet will help motivate readers to learn. We can use pictures, films, and music to combine with the lessons to increase their intellectual awareness and develop their thinking ability. Another benefit is that students can use English-related apps on their phones. According to Speck (2019), English language learners will benefit if they approach technology. Nowadays, we are using technology in many different ways, especially in education. Hopkins

(2017) said that people just knew something close to them in the past. However, technology has changed all their minds. Now students can communicate with their friends, family, and teachers immediately via smartphones. Furthermore, Motteram (2014) claimed that the users such as teachers and students could access the Internet to seek various information and debate with their classmates about what they have just found out in the world. Thank you for technology, especially the Internet, learners can access to studying easily. Learners can broaden their study extent when they have classes supported by technology (Larsen- Freeman and Anderson, 2011). According to Ahmadi (2018), technology makes learners study smoothly, but we should be considered using it as a support tool in learning. There are several methods in teaching vocabularies, such as using mobile phones or mobile applications. Furthermore, these things also accept learners to learn beyond the classroom. On the other hand, teaching activities will not restrict the places everywhere that students can take part with their lecturers and other students (Hashemifardnia, 2018). Computer technology and the Internet will use the benefits of studying, enhancing, rehearsing, and developing speaking skills. EFL students can use some technology such as computers, tablets, and Smartphones to access the Internet to communicate with foreigners and improve the language (Alsied and Pathan, 2013).

1.2. Statement of the problems

Using technology has become popular with everybody in every area. Especially in the Covid-19 pandemic is spreading worldwide, so many countries have been applying technology to learning, specifically in learning English. For example, in Vietnam, there are a lot of schools, colleges, and universities that use technology in learning. However, many students and teachers have some difficulties using technology to learn English. For instance, students and teachers hardly connect together, or teachers cannot motivate students as traditional learning. Therefore, they do not want to use technology in learning.

On the other hand, using technology still has become more general, including learning English. The reason for using technology in learning English more widely is that it has many advantages. For instance, pronunciation will be improved by using pronunciation test apps. Communication skills also will be more proficient. Furthermore, technology helps education be expanded, and modern technology supports people to achieve many outstanding achievements in future learning, particularly in learning English.

1.3. The purpose of the study

The main purpose of this research is to clarify the benefits that technology brings to students and teachers.

1.4. Significance of the study

Large numbers of research papers have provided advantages from the use of technology in language learning. Technology helps educators and learners have more options for English learning. This below is how technology brings benefits for students and teachers:

- Students can use educational apps such as Elsa, Duolingo, etc., to improve their vocabulary and pronunciation.
- In the Covid-19 pandemic, technology allows students to connect to teachers while away from class.
- Technology gives teachers a lot of software to create more life-like lessons for students.

2. PREVIOUS REVIEW

2.1. Theory review

What is technology? Technology is the invention, change, use, and knowledge of tools, machines, techniques, professional skills, systems, and organizational methods, to solve a problem, improve an existing solution, achieve a goal, or perform a specific function. Using technology in learning English uses software or applications on phones or computers that can assist in learning. Application software is used, such as Duolingo, Elsa Speaking, Oxford's Dictionary, etc.

2.2. Literature review

There are several surveys and researches for using technology in language learning. In 2016, Alsulami researched intending to find the impact of technology on learning English for female EFL students in Effatt College. He used questionnaires with Likert scale questions for this research. The Statistical Package analyzed this study's data for Social Sciences (SPSS) to obtain results. The findings clearly indicate that social media, software, audio tools (Youtube, Skype, MP3 player), and educational apps on smartphones positively affect. However, the useful impact of using Technology in English learning depends on how students or learners use it.

In 2012, one research was done by Shyamlee and Phil with the topic "Use of Technology in English Language Teaching and Learning". Two authors used qualitative analysis to find out the pros and cons of applying multimedia technology to English language teaching and learning, such as e-mail, the Internet, Electronic Dictionary, PowerPoint, etc. The results obviously show that using multimedia technology can enhance teachers' and students' teaching effect and interaction. Moreover, technology also makes the course content flexible. Everything has two sides, however, technology also keeps students' thinking potential restricted. All in all, the authors claimed that technology should not be overused because it is just a support tool for teaching and learning English.

This article was written by Parvin and Salam (2015). This commentary is related to the value when using technology methods in the English language and improving English skills. Afterward, this writing aims to recommend more

technology devices such as audiovisual materials in the primary schools to develop children's capability in English because the education wants to concentrate on grammar and obliges children to learn by heart the new words in the past. This research's methods were surveyed to analyze the unbelievable changes when applying a new way like audiovisual materials into the primary schools. The following data collection was observed by the team members (2013) that divided into three parts: comparing the different results of examination between ICT and non-ICT, paying attention to the debated team between students and teachers, and the last one is monitoring devices at school that includes the number of observation type such as Classes is over 50, Classes have a recorded video that is 13, Observed Classes without ICT are 33. The main results make people know about ICT and non-ICT schools, the debating team, and class observation. Furthermore, these findings want the other people to understand more about the changes when comparing use or do not use technology and also create innovation when applying it to education in successful ways.

Another research was done by Patel (2015) with the topic Significance of Technology Enhanced Language Learning (TELL) in Language Classes. He used a questionnaire and analysis method for this research. The findings indicate that many opportunities that English teachers created to help students meet their language goals in technology improved language learning in a language environment. All in all, this research makes an effort to outline some of the trends growing in technology-enhanced language learning.

Technology is popular with everyone in every area, including education. An article was written by Costley (2014) with the topic The Positive Effects of Technology

on Teaching and Student Learning. The author used analysis for this paper. This paper showed that technology has a positive effect on language learning. Moreover, technology is effective in all age groups and helps students with special learning needs. In summary, using technology in learning English has many following benefits: increased student motivation, engagement, collaboration, and technology skills.

This article was written by Rahami and Katal (2012) to show the innovation of using podcasting technology in studying a language. This writing illustrates the

estimation of students when using a metacognitive listening skill. Besides that, the purposes of this observation are to reveal the position of methods awareness about metacognitive listening skills and ready to use technology in podcasting for studying English. This survey analyzes how using podcasting technology affects university students. Afterward, students introduce using podcasting technology and making it more helpful. Those students are also participants of this research, with 141 people from four universities. This study accounts for almost 41% masculine and 60% feminine students. Then, the sample (about 90%) argues digital devices that can be used to electronic devices. The main results want to teach university students to have more knowledge about metacognitive listening skills, and through using podcasting technology in studying English, the necessary things of students are attitude, understanding, or experience.

The authors of this research are Yang and Chen (2007) to reveals the influence of using Internet devices in learning English as a foreign language. This commentary lets students have more opportunities to use technology in the foundation course. This study's main purpose lets students know if students study English through multimedia technology, it will require new studying methods and self-directed studying. The participants have 44 people to complete this research paper, and all of the participants are masculine students in the grade tenth. Besides that, 12% never uses the Internet before, 88% left has experience of using technology devices (Internet, e-mail, and so on). Data collection divides into many parts such as discussion, questionnaires, document analysis, and e-mail. This research wants to show technology devices that can be useful for enhancing students' English skills, even for teaching methods, and improving communication skills.

Fithriani (2019) study to investigate the popular media in Indonesia - Facebook - is indeed a useful learning tool that EFL university students use in their classroom learn to write advanced. The researcher used questionnaires, discussions, and interviews on Facebook with 53 students, including 40 female students and 13 male students. The results show that using Facebook in the writing classroom has helped students boost their confidence, communication skills and improve their English, especially writing skills. The study's conclusion has

confirmed that Facebook is an effective learning tool for students in their classes.

Another study did by Trasierra in 2018 with the main purpose is to analyze the disadvantages and advantages of using Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in English as a Foreign Language (EFL). The research paper participant is Primary Education English teachers in Catalonia, and the data collection has collected in questionnaires by Google form. Through surveys, he has analyzed teacher vision problems in using technology in the classroom. This research's limitation is the results are based on limited data collection. And the author considers having more studies in terms of the disadvantages of ICTs in English learning.

The article is observed by Mofareh (2019) to demonstrate the positive outcomes of technology after using technology in education. For our research, the study wants to change the old teaching methods into modern methods such as using technology. This is because the old teaching research has some problems that are not as expected. Students and teachers are the participants in our research. Besides that, the research paper reveals between 75% and 85% that students accept these traditional teaching methods, from 60% to 80% that students do not pleased with these methods to study. The final results want students to have more confidence to achieve with flying colors in English and show more traditional teaching methods.

2.3. Research question

The paper will provide us the answer to the following questions:

What technologies (social media, computer software, audio tools, and educational apps) do learners use in learning English?

What have been the positive results of using technology in learning English?

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research context

Van Lang University was established in 1995. The president of this university is a professional Tran Thi My Dieu. Nowadays, Van Lang has three campuses. The head

office is located in district 1, the second campus located in Binh Thanh district, and the last campus is located in Go Vap district. Van Lang is a private university that has 30 faculties. Each year, about 17.000 new students enroll in this school. Van Lang University not only has the slogan of Van Lang, which is Morality-Will-Creativity but also has a song called "Van Lang Dai Hoc Duong".

3.2. Population and sampling method

Our research's goals focus on the faculty of a foreign language, and the participants are the junior students. We feel these students are a suitable object to complete our research topic because of the same major.

We choose a convenient method to make completely sampling methods. Our group will divide into three steps:

- The first step: we listed each subject's class that we studied to know the population in every single class.
- The second step: we printed the research paper in every class's exact population and checked the questions again.
- The third step: we gave the paper to the students, and we asked them to fill in to finish research questions.

3.3. Research design

We choose Questionnaire and Interview to survey this study.

We make 19 questions for questionnaires and ten questions for interviews.

In questionnaires, number 1 to number 4 questions answer for the first research question. The rest of the questions answers for the second research question.

In the interview, we have number 1 answers for the first research question and number 2 to number 10 answers for the second research question.

3.4. Data collection

We collected data by Questionnaire and Interview at Van Lang University during a week. We surveyed by giving 288 questionnaires to third-year students in the Faculty of Foreign Languages, and we have obtained 288 responses for this. We also interviewed 10 students for this research.

3.5. Procedure

We wrote questionnaires and interview based on two research question:

- What technology (social media, computer software, audio tools, and educational apps) learners use to learn English?
- What have been the positive results of using technology in learning English?

We have discussed how to create questions that satisfy two research questions. After that, we printed 300 questionnaires and ten interview questions to give third-year undergraduates in the Faculty of Foreign Languages. We started giving them from Nov 9-14, 2020, and on Nov 15, 2020, we analyzed the data.

We went to each class that third-year students were studying and asked for the teacher's permission. Each survey students take about two to three minutes, only about 10 minutes for interviews.

3.6. Data analyze

After collecting evaluation data on the study:

- Summary and categorization of data.
- Then present the data regarding the number of examples, questions percent... by the graph.
- Firstly, 'Descriptive Statistics' is used to describe data.

- After that, 'Inference statistics' helps to compare data.

4. RESULTS

4.1. The demographic data of participants

Relating to survey participants, 288 students were surveyed for the effectiveness of using technology in learning English. All of them are third-year students in the foreign language departments of Van Lang University. The participants were studying in the first semester of the academy year. We have decided to select junior students for the survey because we are also junior students of the university, which helps us have more advantages in getting opinions such as arranging time easily.

4.2. Research question 1

What technologies (social media, computer software, audio tools, and educational apps) do learners use in learning English?

Question number 1 to number 4 in questionnaires answers the research question 1, which was created to explore what kind of technologies students often use in their English learning (question 3). Questions 2 and 4 have explored participants' feelings when using technology to study English. And number 1 has discovered the way that students often learn English.

Chart 1. The way of student practice English.

Chart 1 shows how students practice English. As indicated in the questionnaires, students have chosen technology to learn English by 68.8%. This number shows that the application of technology to learn

English is no longer unfamiliar to students. And it is really beneficial, so the percentage of students who chose to study with technology is so much. 43.3% of students have chosen to practice individually. This is

also a pretty large percentage. It means that students are hesitant about learning with others even though they practice English very effectively. Studying alone can also bring great results, but it is very difficult to help you spot mistakes as easily as studying with fellow students.

Chart 2: Technology is useful for students in learning English

Chart 3. The feeling of participants when using technology in learning English

Chart 2 and chart 3 reveal that the number of students choosing technology useful for learning English and easily using is a lot, the rate is 96% and 91%, respectively. It means that technology really works for them and they like applying it, and it hard for any disadvantages to the learners. They can be easily accessed anytime and anywhere. 4% of students think that technology is not beneficial. That is a very small percentage, but it is shown that they maybe have not applied technology in the right way, so it has not worked for them yet. In addition, 9% of participants said that using technology to learn is difficult. This number suggests that there are still some limitations. For instance, students must have an internet connection to use English learning apps, or students are bothered by advertisements while studying on software or computer.

Chart 4. The kind of technology that participants apply to learn English

This chart shows the most common technology that learners regularly use to learn English. As can be seen, the highest percentage of all cases is educational apps (75.30%). It means that the learning apps are very popular among students, and those are easy to download and easy to use. Nevertheless, smartphones

and tablets were also selected by many students (60.80%). As you know, Smartphones are a kind of technology that almost everyone has today. Students choose smartphones and tablets to learn English because they are so compact and have many features to aid in learning. And learners can carry them easily.

To sum, the data from question 1 to question 4 indicated that the use of technology in learning English is increasingly popular and effective for students. Furthermore, the data also shows that it is easier for learners to study technology. Some kinds of technologies like educational apps, smartphones, tablets are used the most by learners for their convenience. However, technology in learning English also has a few limitations, such as having a lot of advertising while studying and having to have an internet connection to learn.

In this study, we have 10 questions for interviews, and questions number 1 and 2 will show us the answer to research question 1. We interview face-to-face with 10 junior students to have in-depth information for the research question. The participants in the interview are coded S1, S2, to S10. We create question 1 to want to know which technologies students use the most in learning English. S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8, and S10 said that smartphones are used the most. However, S9 has used computers the most. This result shows that smartphones are really good tools for English. It is very small but contains a lot of information and data. Moreover, students can download learning software or information to their smartphones to study anywhere and anytime. Those are the reason smartphones are so popular in English learning. Furthermore, question 2 helps us explore the purpose of students when using technology in learning English.

The main purpose when I using technology is looking up a dictionary, consulting friends, improving listening skills, and learning new words.

Student 1

The purpose is to use a dictionary online to search for new words and translating.

Student 2

My purpose is to use the Internet to search for information for a research paper, using an online dictionary to find out the meaning of new words, discussing with my fellow student through Messenger when we are at home.

Student 3

The purposes are enhancing vocabulary and 4 English skills: reading, listening, writing, and speaking.

Student 4, 5, and 6

My aim is to seek many vocabularies and checking pronunciation.

Student 7

I think my purpose is to communicate with foreigners.

Student 8

I want to take part in the English clubs on Facebook.

Student 9

The purposes: accessing information and finding new words in the dictionary online.

Student 10

In general, the main purpose has given the most of the responses is using an online dictionary and improve their 4 English skills. It means that in learning a foreign language, it is necessary to understand the meaning of the words, so students use the dictionary online. However, in some cases, the students depend too much on the dictionary. In addition, 4 English skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing is also mentioned. As can be seen, students are also increasingly focusing on all skills rather than just focusing on listening or speaking.

To summarize the interview, the answer to research question 1 was clearly that smartphones are applied the most by students while learning English because they give us a flexible ability to download and access information. Besides, using online dictionaries and enhancing their English skills is the main purpose of using technology. An online dictionary helps students have the opportunity to an in-depth understanding of the meaning of new words. And focusing on 4 English skills will help them become more fluent in English.

4.3. Research question 2

What have been the positive results of using technology in learning English?

Question number 5 to number 12 of the questionnaire, which was designed to explore how four English skills of third-year students in Van Lang

University applied technology in learning English. And question number 5 has explored the first skill.

Chart 5. Speaking skills have been enhanced after using technology in learning English

As can be seen in chart 5, about 96% of students in Van Lang University said "Yes" to this question. This explains that speaking skills have improved the most after using technology in learning English. And the rest of 4% is that students still cannot improve their speaking skills through study with technological devices.

Chart 6. The percentage of speaking skills have been enhanced after using technology

Chart 6 reveals that students' speaking skills have improved at an average level is 57%. This implicated that speaking skills are enhanced significantly when students apply technology to learning English. Moreover, this percentage also showed that students apply the right technology to learning English, so it brings students amazing results. For example, they can use smartphones to call foreigners to practice speaking. Next, about 23% is the percentage of the level of the improvement more than 80% of students after using technology in learning English. It shows that their speaking skill is likely to improve a lot after using technological devices in learning English.

Although the percentage of the improvement level is more than 80%, which is still low, this number shows that students know how to use technology in learning English. The remainder of this question's percentage is 20% presented that using technology in learning English is not as helpful as they expected.

Chart 7. Listening skills have been developed after using technology in learning English

As can be seen from data in chart 7, it showed that 96% of students at Van Lang University said "Yes" to this question. This explains that listening skill has been improved a lot after using technology in learning English. And the rest of the 4% is that students still cannot improve their listening skills through study with technology.

Chart 8. The percentage of listening skills have been developed after using technology

Chart 8 showed that students' listening skills have improved at an average level of 40%. This implicated that listening skills increased not very much when students apply technology to learning English. Furthermore, this number also shows that students apply technology correctly to studying English. Next, about 36% showed that their listening skills had been enhanced the most (more than 80% of listening skills) after using technological devices to learn English. This percent is extremely high. This explains that students

know exactly how to use technological devices in learning English, and technology helps them practice listening skills. They improve their listening skills by more than 80% because they always listen to English songs and stories or news in English on Youtube like VOA Learning English or learning apps supporting students to practice listening. The rest of the percentage of this question is 24% presented that using technology in learning English is useful for them to study English.

Chart 9. Reading skills have been improved after using technology in learning English

Our research paper stated that 95% of students at Van Lang University said "Yes" to this question. This explains that reading skills have been enhanced significantly after using technology to learn English. And the rest of the 5% is that students still cannot improve their reading skills by studying technology.

Chart 10. The percentage of reading skills have been improved after using technology

This chart presented that students' reading skills have improved at an average level is 58%. This implicated that listening skills increased rather well when students apply technology to learning English. In addition, this explains that almost all students usually apply technological devices to learning English,

especially in reading skills. Thanks to technology and the Internet, students can read more and more online newspapers and English stories to be experts at reading skills. Next, about 14% showed that their reading skill is likely to improve not much after applying technology to learning English. The rest of this question's percentage is 28% (level of improvement at 30%). It shows that the improvement of reading skills is very low. This number presented that using technology in learning English is not as useful as they wanted.

Chart 11. Writing skills have been improved after using technology in learning English

As can be seen in this chart, about 94% of students at Van Lang University said "Yes" to this question. This explains that writing skill has been improved the most after using technology in learning English. And the rest of the 6% is that students still cannot improve their writing skills through study with technological devices.

Chart 12. The percentage of writing skills have been improved after using technology

This chart showed that 51% of reading skills had been improved at a weak level. This number indicated that using technological devices in learning English is not

helpful. Students cannot know exactly how to use technology to improve their writing skills, so they feel that their writing skills have been improved when they study with their face-to-face instructors. However, writing skill has improved at an average level is 31%. This implicated that listening skills enhanced but not much when students apply technology to learning English. This percent also shows that many students still apply technology to learning English. For example, they can enhance their writing skills through Grammarly apps or check plagiarism apps to prevent them from having some plagiarism and grammar mistakes when they practice writing in English. Next, about 18% showed that their writing skill is likely to improve not much after applying technology to learning English.

In sum, question 5 to question 12 indicates that listening skill has been improved the most in four English skills surveyed by third-year students at Van Lang University. On the other hand, writing skills increased not as much as listening skills. Finally, the rest of the two skills (speaking and reading skills) were enhanced sufficiently. All four English skills have been improved significantly by studying with technological devices.

In the interview, question number 6 to question number 9 will show us the answers to research question 2. We interviewed person-in-person 10 students to have in-depth information for this research question. The participants in this interview will be coded S1, S2 to S10. We create question 6 in order to know how effective technology in speaking skills. According to S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, and S10, they said that:

My speaking skill has been improved a lot.

Student 1, 5, 7, 8, and 9

Speaking skill has been enhanced averagely.

Student 4 and 10

Technological devices are not helpful for me in practicing a speaking skill at all.

Student 2, 3, and 6

We design question number 7 to explore how listening skills developed after using technology to learn

English. Also, we have an interview face-to-face with 10 students at Van Lang University.

Technology helps me improve my listening skills a lot because I usually practice listening skills through Youtube videos.

Student 1, 5, 6, 7, and 8

My listening skill has been improved but not much.

Student 2, 3, 4, 9, and 10

Question number 8 was created to know how reading skills improved after using technology to learn English.

I enhance my reading skill at an average level, learn some new words and read newspapers in English.

Student 2, 3, 4, 8, and 9

My reading has been improved not much.

Student 5, 7, and 10

I do not improve my reading skill at all.

Student 1 and 6

Question number 9 was designed to get how writing skills improved after using technology in learning English.

My writing skill has been improved a lot by using Grammarly and Check Plagiarism apps.

Student 1, 3, 7, 8, 9, and 10

My writing has been enhanced averagely.

Student 4 and 6

I do not use technology to practice my writing skill.

Student 2 and 5

To summarize the interview, we designed these questions in the interview to answer research question 2. We find that there are different answers to each question. Generally, all four skills have been improved. However, there will be various levels for each skill. Firstly, speaking skill has been improved averagely. Next, reading and writing skills have not been enhanced much. Finally, listening skills are improved the most when using technology to support their learning English.

Next, from question 13 to question 19 are the small questions of research question 2 to meet learners' necessities when they want to know more about the benefits of using technology in learning English. For questions 13 and question 14, they illustrate how using pronunciation test software corrects the fault when we speak English. Afterward, quizzes 15 and 16 explore

some advantages of using an online dictionary to meet the study. Besides that, from question 17 to question 19 want to seek learners' enjoyment when applying technology into education. Finally, question 13 to question 19 plays a significant role that finds out how many percentages learners improve after using technology in learning English.

Chart 13. Pronunciation has been better after using pronunciation test software

Chart 13 shows data about how many learners affect pronunciation after using the software. 64% is the highest rate in this chart, and it represents that students improve a lot after using the software and still limit to use technology a lot. Besides that, the learners account for 34% who develop English skills after using technology and know-how to use it efficiently. The lowest rate is 2%, which means that most learners also know to use technology to complete the study's task. It has very few people who do not know the advantages of using technology to learn English.

Chart 14. How pronunciation test software helps students

As can be seen in chart 14, it divides into three rates, which make learners know the significant role in pronunciation when speaking English. The highest rate (67%) expresses that learners use the software to find out the pronunciation's faults to know which words they pronounce false. Besides,

the rate is 50.90% that the rate illustrates learners want the software to check pronunciation and fix it when learners pronounce false. The last rate accounts for 27.40%, which means that very few people know this utility and do not care about this one's benefits.

Chart 15. How online dictionaries bring students benefits

This chart reveals that how online dictionaries easily to use. The highest rate is 56.10% that represents learners can access the dictionaries wherever, whenever, because it does not limit some aspects. 48.10% is the second rate, which means the advantages of online dictionaries help learners easily find the words that learners want. Moreover, there are many online dictionaries on the Internet, so learners have many choices to decide. The part "easy to understand" accounts for 23.30%, which shows that there are still some restricted areas that online dictionaries cannot explain clearly to learners.

Chart 16. The usage of the dictionary helps students more confident when you speak English with many new words

Chart 16 illustrates how the influence of the dictionary affects speaking skills. It seems that most learners feel they improve a lot after using it, but there are still some areas that learners do not understand (65%). The average rate is 30% that describes some learners when using a dictionary, they feel more confident speaking with native speakers, and they easily use a dictionary. The lowest rate is 5%, which means that very few people do not improve by using a dictionary.

As can be seen from the data in chart 17, it shows the necessity when applying technology in learning English classroom. The highest rate accounts for 81%, which illustrates the number of people who agree to use technology that provides many benefits to help learners understand lessons. The second rate

is 15%, which represents that some students understand very little about using technology in the classroom because the technology still argues in learning English also teaching. The last rate accounts for 4%, which means some people do not like this type of study. It seems that they feel easily understand when studying in the traditional classroom.

Chart 17. Using technology in learning English classroom will make it easier to understand the lesson

Chart 18. Using technology will increase students' enjoyment of learning English

Chart 18 relates to students' feelings when applying technology in learning English. The highest number accounts for 93%, which represents that learners feel excited when using technology and help them boost their pleasure in studying English. 7% left that means very few people do not like this way of studying.

Chart 19. How technologies increase students' enjoyment of learning English

The last chart provides that technology affects students' feelings in which way, and there are many ways to make students feel interested in learning English. Reducing boredom in the classroom is 60.10% that means students like applying some modern devices into education to make learners have more opportunities, which can decline the sadness in class. 49% stands for the number of learners who feel communication between students and teacher increase a lot based on using technology. The last rate is 35.80%, which describes the lessons as more interesting, lively, and easy to understand for learners after using technology to learn English.

To sum up, questions 13 to question 19 want to know how many percentages of the participants feel that using technology in the classroom. Furthermore, we estimate how people's rate effects after using technology in studying English. Afterward, we emphasize some apps that can make learners improve a lot and pay attention to learners' emotions to seek the best way that is suitable for learners.

Interview questions 3, 4, 5, and 10 create to investigate the influence of using technology in studying English. Our team members interview face-to-face 10 participants and record their voices to collect the data for these four questions. To question 3 relates to the benefits of using technology in learning English:

I can access sources and information easily anywhere and anytime.

Student 1 and 6

The benefits of using technology in learning English: enhancing vocabulary.

Student 2

The benefits: providing abilities to access sources, watching many videos in terms of how to improve English on Youtube.

Student 3

There is no limitation of information and document on the Internet.

Student 4

Technology helps me find out and correct some mistakes in pronunciation.

Student 5

I can improve pronunciation better, know more vocabularies, more structures

Student 7

I have a chance to earn money

Student 8

I feel more convenient when using technology in learning English

Student 9

Technology provides different opportunities to make learning more fun and enjoyable

- Student 10
Continue with question 4, it relates to using technology affects which skills in English:
- Speaking skills are improved a lot because I keen to learn British accents so I just search on Youtube about it and practice day by day. It helps me a lot.
- Student 1
I think my listening and speaking skills have improved a lot because there are many sources to download and practice on the Internet.
- Student 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10
I think reading skills and writing skills have improved a lot because I usually read online newspapers and journal articles to have new words for my reading skills and use Grammarly for my writing skills.
- Student 3
My writing skill is improved a lot after using technology in learning English.
- Student 4
Moreover, question 5 illustrate the impact of technology in learning English
- Technology is one way to raise English skills, but it still bases on learning. If they learn hard, they will be better. And if they don't, then technology doesn't help. I have improved my speaking skills a lot through media and Youtube.
- Student 1
Technology affects my listening skill a little bit.
- Student 2, 6, and 9
Technology helps me reduce boredom when learning English. There are many educational apps that the very vivid interface.
- Student 3
Technology affects me a little bit. Technology just helps me improve my vocabulary and writing skills.
- Student 4
Instead of studying in books, learning with technology has made me more active, interested.
- Student 10
The last question is number 10; it commends about the pronunciation part.
- I think I can be fluent in pronunciation through some foreigners on social media.
- Student 1, 4
My pronunciation has enhanced, like clearer pronunciation.
- Student 2, 5, 8
My pronunciation also has improved too much. I can pronounce correctly American accent through Elsa App.
- Student 3
My pronunciation improved slightly after using technology to correct my pronunciation mistakes.
- Student 6
I think technology helps me pronounce more correctly and clearly.
- Student 7 and 8
Learn English through phone apps that support speech recognition. From there, I can correct the voice and practice to have a correct voice.
- Student 10
To wrap up, those questions want to investigate some aspects that help learners have real experiences in learning English based on using technology and illustrate which skills after using technology will improve a lot. Besides that, our research emphasizes the influence of using test software or using online

dictionaries in learning English classroom and attaches special importance to the learner's feelings when applying many ways to study English.

5. DISCUSSION

Most of the research papers in the literature review have studied a small part of the English language. On the other hand, our study focuses on English skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Comparative with Alsulami (2016) research paper, he found that the participants always use smartphones (52.8%). Besides, Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and Blogs always are used a lot (50%). However, our study showed that the participants use educational apps the most (75.30%).

There are several different methods between our research and the article "The Effectiveness of Using Technology in English Language Classrooms in Government Primary Schools in Bangladesh" wrote by Parvin and Salam (2015). The first thing, the participants of our topic will focus on students more. Nevertheless, the research paper on google scholar concentrated on teachers more. On the other hand, our methods aim at collecting the rate of developed skills after using technology in learning English. In contrast, the authors' research investigates how some devices (audio-visual content) affect education.

Another comparison that demonstrates our topic is the article "The role of metacognitive listening strategies awareness and podcast-use readiness in using podcasting for learning English as a foreign language" by Rahimi and Katal (2012). Our topic's participants emphasize using technology (mobile phones or computers) to study English. However, the research paper's participants choose the form of using podcasting technology to enhance English skills.

The research paper "Technology-enhanced language learning: A case study" from Yang and Chen (2006) clearly shows the differences with our group's topic. Our research illustrates technology that will have more opportunities to develop our English skills. On the other hand, the authors' study reveals that video conferencing promotes English communication skills.

In the study "Using Facebook in EFL Writing Class: Its Effectiveness from Students' Perspective" by Fithriani (2019), Facebook is social media that the participants of this study use the most, with a total of 52 users. By contrast, we just focus on smartphones and computers because we think that Facebook is on smartphones and computers.

Shyamlee and Phil (2012) showed that there are many kinds of technological devices used in teaching and learning English like Radio, Electronic Dictionary, computers, and so on. Specifically, our research indicates that students use Educational apps, smartphones, Audio tools, Computer, (75.30%, 60.80%, 19.40%, and 19.10% respectively).

In Costley's (2014) study, he claimed that technology is the best tool for students to learn. Comparing our research with his paper shows that using technology in learning differently. In his research, Wiki technology helps students a lot because students receive feedback immediately from the instructor to use this form of technology. On the other hand, our research shows that writing skill has been improved a little (30%).

Patel's (2017) research, Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) is very useful for students in speaking and writing in a foreign language. According to our research, technology helps the student improve their speaking skill a lot (57%) and writing skill at a low level (31%).

"The Use of Technology in English Language Teaching" by Mofareh (2009) has different methods from ours. Our group's topic emphasizes technology, which is crucial in learning English. Nevertheless, the research paper showed that students achieved high-level English skills by 75-95% when teachers used modern teaching techniques.

In the literature review, Trasierra (2018) study has shown the advantages and disadvantages of using ICTs in the classroom. Comparative with our study, the participants of his study have just focused on teachers. However, the ICTs tools that help students improve listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills are computer, Youtube, dictionary online, Duolingo, etc. It is a similar result to our research paper.

6. CONCLUSION

Data from question 1 to question 4 in the study suggest that the use of technology in learning English is becoming increasingly widespread and productive for learners. Besides, knowledge also can learn from technology more easily. Due to its usability, certain kinds of technology such as educational apps, smartphones, and tablets are often used by learners. However, using technology in learning English still has some drawbacks, such as certain commercials and an internet connection to learn while using. Data from sentences 5 to 12 indicate that of the four English skills surveyed by 3rd-year students at Van Lang University, listening abilities are the most enhanced. On the other hand, writing skills have not increased as much. Finally, the remaining two skills have been strengthened (speaking and reading skills). By studying with technical devices, all 4 English skills are greatly improved. Furthermore, question 13 to Question 19 would like to know how many percentages of respondents believe that they use technology in the classroom. Besides, we estimate how individuals' rate influences the study of English after using technology. Subsequently, we highlight some programs that can help learners change a lot and pay attention to learners' feelings to find the best approach that is acceptable for learners.

A very important role is played by searching and analyzing data. It is not easy to acquire the data. Researchers have to ask questions and collect them afterward. Currently, this research has not reached all students at Van Lang University studying English. 288 students collected the results of the questionnaire, and 10 students were interviewed (this result is too few). 3rd-year students conducted the research, so it had not connected students in other disciplines as well as in other years.

The results showed that using technology in learning English is very important. so it is even more important to get data and collect opinions. Researchers need to pay more attention when choosing this research paper's participants, such as taking data from all students studying English and other disciplines to get diverse and objective details. Only focus on the questionnaire really associated with using technology to learn English and interviewing 15-20 questions directly with students at

school. Can send these questionnaires to students of other schools if there are time and opportunity. This will help to enrich the database.

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